

THE VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY WITH CONCENTRATION OF WEAK ELECTROLYTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND A. N. BOSE

The variations of specific conductivity of weak electrolytes with concentration has been studied in non-aqueous solvents. It has been observed that the solutions can be divided into two categories :

(i) The solutions which give a straight line plot or nearly so for $\mu \cdot c$ within the concentration range studied here.

(ii) The plot of $\mu \cdot c$ shows a maximum. In some cases the first concentration of the solute is so high that further addition of the solute diminishes the conductivity.

It has been suggested that if the relative increase in the viscosity is more than the relative increase in the specific conductivity with increasing concentration then a maximum is obtained in the plot of $\mu \cdot c$.

The variation of specific conductivity with concentration of the aqueous solutions of electrolytes has been studied by several workers. Jones, Blitz and their collaborators (Jones, "Hydrates in Aqueous Solutions", 1907, pp. 840, 907) measured the conductivity of aqueous solutions of CoCl_2 and CuCl_2 in presence of various dehydrating agents and noticed a maximum in the plot of $\mu \cdot c$ and suggested that it was due to the increase in the viscosity of the solutions. Usanovitsch (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1940, 10, 59) pointed out that the maximum in the $\mu \cdot c$ curve was either due to complex formation or due to opposing forces of viscosity and concentration.

Ram Gopal (Thesis, Lucknow University, 1946) studied the variation of specific conductivity with concentration for supersaturated aqueous solutions and pointed out that the solutions could be divided into two categories. In category one belong the substances which have very little hydrating power and hence a lower viscosity. Substances of the second category pass through a maximum at ordinary concentrations.

From the above consideration it appears that practically no work has been done on the variation of specific conductivity with concentration for the non-aqueous solutions of weak electrolytes, especially when highly concentrated and supersaturated solutions are taken.

Experimental method followed is the same as given in a previous communication (this issue, p. 138). The results obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I

The variation of specific conductivity with concentration.

Concentration is given in g. of solute per 100 g. of solvent.

Solute.	Temp.	Solvent = Acetone.				
		<i>c</i> =				
Benzoic acid	35°	52.54	59.44	66.97	72.41	} × 10 ⁻⁷
	45°	7.420	7.095	6.873	6.541	
Salicylic acid	30°	48.47	56.42	63.73	70.33	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	1.752	1.772	1.756	1.765	
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	25°	74.01	81.91	106.10	113.00	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	4.578	4.456	4.190	3.908	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	25°	50.22	59.75	79.95	90.60	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	1.713	1.758	1.796	1.809	
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	25°	22.20	32.40	70.50	89.10	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	1.689	2.778	4.365	4.922	
Cinnamic acid	30°	19.26	32.92	38.65	44.16	} × 10 ⁻⁷
	45°	7.663	9.430	9.772	9.799	
Phthalic acid	30°	1.705	3.490	5.354	6.473	} × 10 ⁻⁷
	45°	5.723	6.836	7.421	8.716	
Oxalic acid	25°	4.504	12.49	24.74	32.16	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	45°	4.220	8.664	14.580	18.130	
Succinic acid	35°	1.626	3.264	5.110	6.868	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	45°	1.604	2.566	3.388	4.148	
Solvent = Methyl alcohol.						
Benzoic acid	35°	72.21	77.63	82.55	90.55	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	4.689	4.303	4.276	3.981	
Salicylic acid	30°	52.97	58.78	64.36	68.74	} × 10 ⁻⁶
	45°	3.470	3.302	3.310	3.271	
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	25°	57.24	81.91	106.10	113.00	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	45°	4.578	4.456	4.190	3.908	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	25°	28.66	55.50	73.03	89.24	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	45°	1.526	1.570	1.456	1.362	
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	35°	35.81	42.45	53.65	60.42	} × 10 ⁻⁵
	45°	5.645	6.247	6.533	6.627	

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Temp.	Solvent=Methyl alcohol.					
Cinnamic acid	25°	$c =$	19.22	26.76	33.54	40.40	} $\times 10^{-5}$
	45°		0.9268	0.8537	0.8018	0.7390	
Phthalic acid	30°	$c =$	19.48	27.81	34.43	44.40	} $\times 10^{-5}$
	45°		4.539	4.677	4.617	---	
Solvent=Propyl alcohol.							
Benzoic acid	30°	$c =$	24.10	32.53	43.03	58.11	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		2.198	2.034	1.918	1.789	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	30°	$c =$	60.93	70.55	83.90	94.74	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		1.622	1.581	1.381	1.497	
Cinnamic acid	30°	$c =$	11.05	22.19	28.50	33.15	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		5.624	6.511	6.466	6.410	
Phthalic acid	25°	$c =$	5.05	7.25	9.21	11.00	} $\times 10^{-5}$
	45°		2.387	2.097	2.038	3.182	
Succinic acid	25°	$c =$	1.945	3.174	4.922	8.468	} $\times 10^{-6}$
	45°		3.294	4.919	6.610	9.004	
Oxalic acid	35°	$c =$	16.03	26.45	44.30	57.34	} $\times 10^{-5}$
	45°		9.330	23.990	44.640	61.140	
Solvent= <i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol.							
Salicylic acid	35°	$c =$	18.62	22.72	17.72	33.25	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		6.255	7.075	7.428	7.947	
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	25°	$c =$	11.80	20.77	30.94	46.93	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		5.991	7.755	9.440	10.400	
<i>o</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	25°	$c =$	4.35	12.10	18.10	22.00	} $\times 10^{-7}$
	45°		1.724	2.630	2.981	3.298	
Succinic acid	35°	$c =$	1.150	2.620	3.728	5.609	} $\times 10^{-6}$
	59°		1.463	2.071	3.452	4.337	
Phthalic acid	35°	$c =$	2.266	4.256	6.714	10.600	} $\times 10^{-6}$
	45°		1.009	1.385	1.713	1.829	

NOTE: (1) Specific conductivity has been determined at five different temperatures but due to brevity of space it is given at two different temperatures.

(2) 'c' denotes the concentration in g. of solute per 100 g. of solvent.

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Table I specific conductivity has been plotted against concentration. The results for the plot of $\mu \cdot c$ can be divided into two categories :

(i) Those that give a straight line plot or nearly so, e. g. solutions of oxalic and phthalic acid in propyl alcohol and oxalic acid in acetone.

(ii) Those that pass through a maximum, e. g. solutions of benzoic acid in methyl and propyl alcohols, *o*-aminobenzoic acid in butyl alcohol, etc. In some cases the concentration of the solute is so high that further addition of the solute diminishes the conductivity, e. g. in solutions of cinnamic acid and *o*-nitrobenzoic acid in methyl alcohol, etc.

Solutions of the second type show a maximum probably due to the fact that as the concentration increases, the viscosity increases, but if the relative increase in the viscosity is more than the relative increase in the conductivity then the plot of $\mu \cdot c$ should pass through a maximum ; whereas in those solutions in which a straight line plot is obtained, the above two increases are proportional to the increase in concentration.

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